

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19966235>

FROM PLAY TO PROFICIENCY: GAMIFICATION IN VOCABULARY ACQUISITION

Xoshimjonova Sarvinoz Dilmurod qizi

E-mail: xoshimjonova17@gmail.com

student of Namangan State Institute of foreign languages.

Scientific adviser: **Abdusattorova Maxarram Sharifjon qizi**

abdusattorovamuharram929@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to examine how games can impact vocabulary learning among 6th-grade students and to determine students' perceptions of game-based learning in vocabulary acquisition. The research was conducted using a survey model, with a sample that included students from selected 6th-grade classes. Data were collected through a questionnaire designed to identify preferences and difficulties in learning vocabulary. The results of the study revealed that game-based learning significantly improved students' ability to remember and use new vocabulary. Based on these findings, I created a game named "Friendly Crossword" to integrate vocabulary learning with gameplay. The findings suggest that using games, particularly "Friendly Crossword," is an effective and engaging method for improving vocabulary learning among 6th-grade students. This study highlights the importance of interactive and student-centered approaches in language education.

Key words: Vocabulary learning, game-based learning, Friendly Crossword, student motivation, language acquisition.

INTRODUCTION

Learning vocabulary is one of the most essential parts of language learning process as it is main foundation in forming competence in any language skill(listening, reading, writing and speaking). That's why don't we link games to vocabulary to make learning both effective and entertaining.

Background. Vocabulary is the most important thing to be learned. Learning a language will never be successful without learning and understanding the vocabulary. Having good knowledge of vocabulary supports students to master English. Vocabulary is one of the important aspects in learning a foreign language. A limited vocabulary has also a limited understanding in terms of listening, speaking, reading and writing. It is true that it might be impossible to learn a language without mastering vocabulary. Many students cannot read and understand a text which is written in English because they do not have a good command of vocabulary¹. While, in the context of language learning, gamification holds potential for improving vocabulary acquisition. Through the incorporation of game elements into vocabulary instruction, educators can cultivate a more captivating and motivating learning atmosphere. Gamification enhances engagement in e-learning environments, a key factor in vocabulary development². Additionally, Fogg says, Motivation is crucial in learning. If students are not motivated, even if they have the ability to solve a problem, they may not end up solving it. Conversely, if they are highly motivated, even though they have limited ability, motivation will help them to find the means to accomplish a task and eventually enhance the ability³. In turn, Piyoto mixed language learning to both gamification and technology. He studied how using gamification through Quizizz to teach vocabulary to students also provided reduced text anxiety. He considered the impact to the student that uses Quizizz regularly as a formative assessment on the typical anxiety that accommodates many high stakes summative assessments. This is a

¹Muhammad Arsul, 2024. "Raising Engagement in e-Learning through Gamification", - Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Virtual Learning ICVL, 323-329. https://www.icvl.eu/2011/2011/papers/ICVL2011_Paper36.pdf

²Muntean, 2011. "Persuasive technology: Using computers to change what we think and do", - San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers. <https://www.nus.edu.sg/celc/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/13.-Sze-Lui.pdf>

³Fogg, 2002. "Gamification in teaching vocabulary" https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378057187_Gamification_in_Teaching_Vocabulary

multiplayer, student paced game that students were allowed to play on their own devices. Students can select from pre-made quizzes or create their own¹. This research is planned to explore the ways of teaching vocabulary through gamification and the use of technology. It aims to identify various techniques and digital tools that can help increase students' vocabulary knowledge and improve their motivation in learning new words. In addition to this, the study intends to analyze how game-based activities and technological platforms influence students' vocabulary retention, engagement, and participation, which have been less analyzed in some previous studies. This article will contribute to the existing literature by providing information about gamification strategies, technology-based vocabulary teaching methods, teachers' challenges in implementing digital tools, students' attitudes toward game-based learning tasks, and the importance of integrating technology into vocabulary instruction together with practical tips and examples of activities. This research tried to discover following issues and answer these questions.

Picture.1.2 Research questions

5-6th grade students at school 29 in Uychi district, in Namangan were chosen as research subjects. Gamification in vocabulary was prepared according to the procedure used by Piyoto. He applied using formative assessment by using Quizziz instead of tests which cause anxiety. Traditionally, vocabulary competence has been assessed by measuring reading translation skills. However, these students highly fail using these vocabulary actively in writing and speaking as these words fade in students' brain very quickly. To test our primary hypothesis that why they struggle to memorize and use the vocabulary, we conducted a questionnaire among teenagers.

¹Piyoto, 2019. "Teaching vocabulary through Gamification" <https://padlet.com/cynthiakuhlman/teaching-vocabulary-through-gamification-hidv43jlfplmutya/wish/0BA3ZpMjeOB2WnPb>

The design was a mixed-method study, that includes integrating both games and learning into vocabulary learning. Observations were conducted at 29th school among 5th -6th grade students, who were approximately 13 girls and 7 boys. Research is conducted among 5th -6th grade students, who were approximately 13 girls and 7 boys. A major advantage of applying games is that when learning is unconscious it would be easier to teach anything. Vocabulary is crucial in building foundation in any language, so, in turn, it assists learners to develop four major skills. That's why, we should pay attention how to teach it effectively for making it easier for memorizing. The research participants were recruited from local school learners who were studying 6th grade. They were over 20 students (13 girls/7 boys) from two different classes. The data was collected by giving questionnaire to students and interview from teachers in order to identify clearly about what students struggle when memorizing or using vocabulary and what could help them to fix it. Survey results showed that students fail to memorize vocabulary because of lack of practice, word by word translation or difficulty to understand the meaning of some words. Relatively, they pointed using definitions, more practice and playing games can help them to memorize the vocabulary and use them actively. While, I interviewed some of my colleagues to analyze what methods they use to ask vocabulary from students and to make them to use new vocabulary. They also highlighted that vocabulary teaching is really challenging. They mentioned how fast they memorize new words they forget them that quickly.

Vocabulary that is taught is usually divided into two categories: active and passive. When a learner expresses their ideas in a foreign language and understands words used in other people's speech, this vocabulary is called active vocabulary. Passive vocabulary, on the other hand, refers to words that are mainly understood when they are heard or read. Active vocabulary is also called reproductive, while passive

vocabulary is receptive. ¹For instance, students know the words "enjoyable" and "amazing" are synonyms for "interesting", yet they cannot use them instead of it as they are passive vocabulary. The problem is some students have strong memory to learn new words but passively. It means when you ask them they can tell the word or definition clearly, yet still fail to use in reality. Certainly, teachers also recommended me to use more practical activities, clear definitions and games to teach new words better. My independent variable was the impact of gamification in vocabulary learning.

According to the results of the survey, I tried to combine games with word definitions. Based on this idea, and considering the students' age and level, I created a method called the "Friendly Crossword." However, at the beginning I used a traditional method in order to check students' progress. For the research, I selected 10 words from the topic "International Food" from the 6th grade students' textbook. During the first week, I used the traditional word-by-word method and simply asked students to recall the words. In the second week, based on the survey results, I combined definitions with a game and introduced the "Friendly Crossword" activity. In this game, students were divided into groups of about 3–4 members. Each group created a crossword puzzle using the words they had memorized. On the back of the paper, they wrote definitions or questions for the words in the correct order (for example: map – it has seas and rivers, but no water). After that, the groups exchanged their crosswords and solved each other's puzzles. This method was called "Friendly Crossword" because the groups exchanged their work and also kept using their mother tongue while explaining the definitions. This report presents the results of a survey conducted among 20 students, including 13 girls and 7 boys, to investigate their difficulties in learning and remembering new English vocabulary.

¹ Jamol Jalolov- "Foreign language teaching methodology"- "O'qituvchi-Toshkent-2012..

Results. The findings reveal that a majority of students experience challenges in memorizing new words. In particular, 50% of the students reported that learning new vocabulary is very difficult, while 20% find it somewhat difficult. Only 30% of the participants stated that it is not difficult for them. This indicates that vocabulary acquisition is a significant issue for most learners.

Figure 1. The first question analysis.

When asked about the reasons behind these difficulties, 40% of the students explained that they forget words quickly, making it the most common problem. Additionally, 35% admitted that they do not practice enough, which also contributes greatly to their struggles. A smaller number of students (15%) believe that there are simply too many words to learn, while 10% find it difficult to understand the meanings of new words.

Figure 2. The second question analysis.

The survey also explored when students tend to forget vocabulary. The results show that 40% of students forget words when speaking, suggesting a lack of active usage. Meanwhile, 25% forget words after class, 20% during tests, and 15% after a few days. This demonstrates that both immediate and delayed forgetting are common among learners.

Figure 3. . The third question analysis.

In terms of effective learning strategies, students showed a clear preference for interactive methods. Nearly half of the participants (45%) stated that games help them remember vocabulary better. Another 25% prefer using words in sentences, while 20% benefit from repetition. Only 10% find pictures helpful, and none of the students selected writing words as an effective method.

Figure 4. The forth question analysis.

Finally, students were asked how teachers could support them in learning vocabulary. A significant majority (60%) suggested using word games in lessons. Additionally, 25% recommended more practice activities, and 15% preferred clear

explanations of words. Interestingly, none of the students chose the use of pictures as a helpful teaching method.

Figure 5. The fifth question analysis.

The results of the activity showed a clear improvement in students' vocabulary learning when the Friendly Crossword method was applied. During the first week, when the traditional word-by-word method was used, students were asked to recall the target vocabulary items. Out of 20 students, only 6 students were able to provide satisfactory answers, while the rest of the class remembered the words only partially or struggled to recall them correctly. This indicated that simple memorization was not very effective for most learners. However, the situation changed noticeably when the Friendly Crossword activity was introduced in the second week. Through this gamified activity, students were not only able to remember the vocabulary items but also learned how to describe and explain their meanings.

The process of creating crossword puzzles and writing definitions encouraged students to think more deeply about the words and how they were used. As a result,

almost all students actively participated in the activity. Approximately 90% of the students were fully engaged in creating and solving the crosswords within their groups. Even the remaining 10% of students, who sometimes struggled to translate or explain the words in English, were still able to contribute to the activity by using their first language (L1) when necessary. Despite these minor difficulties, they were able to take part in constructing and solving the crossword puzzles and support their group members. Furthermore, after completing the crossword activity, a short question-and-answer session was conducted to check students' vocabulary retention. The results were encouraging: most students were able to recall the words easily without hesitation. In addition, several students went beyond simple recall and were able to create example sentences using the newly learned vocabulary.

DISCUSSION

Naturally, when students learned vocabulary through games, they became more engaged and interested. Additionally, it helped them to understand the meaning of words more deeper than traditional repetitions. Collaboration pushed them to work as a team and how to be responsible when working together with others. The "Friendly Crossword" activity encouraged students to actively use vocabulary rather than simply memorizing words. Working in small groups helped students discuss meanings and remember words more effectively. Writing definitions and solving peers' crosswords reinforced vocabulary understanding. This research supports gamification can always improve students' encouragement to be engaged in any activity. Interactive learning activities often make vocabulary learning more meaningful and memorable for students. However, the study was conducted with a small group of sixth-grade students. The experiment lasted only two weeks, which may not fully show long-term vocabulary retention.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this research was to explore the impact of gamification on vocabulary learning among sixth-grade students. It specifically examined the effectiveness of the Friendly Crossword activity compared to a traditional word-by-word method. The results showed that students were more engaged and remembered vocabulary better when the game-based activity was used. The Friendly Crossword encouraged active participation, collaboration, and deeper understanding of word meanings. The study highlights the importance of integrating gamification into vocabulary teaching. Teachers can improve students' motivation and retention by using interactive activities such as crossword games. Gamified learning environments help students practice vocabulary in a more enjoyable and meaningful way.

REFERENCES:

1. Muhammad Arsul, 2024."Raising Engagement in e-Learning through Gamification", - Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Virtual Learning ICVL,323-329.https://www.icvl.eu/2011/2011/papers/ICVL2011_Paper36.pdf
2. Muntean, 2011."Persuasive technology: Using computers to change what we think and do"
3. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers. <https://www.nus.edu.sg/celc/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/13.-Sze-Lui.pdf>
4. Fogg, 2002."Gamification in teaching vocabulary"https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378057187_Gamification_in_Teaching_Vocabulary
5. Piyoto, 2019."Teaching vocabulary through Gamification"<https://padlet.com/cynthiakuhlman/teaching-vocabulary-through-gamification-hidv43jlfplmutya/wish/0BA3ZpMjeOB2WnPb>
6. Jamol Jalolov- "Foreign language teaching methodology"-“O‘qituvchi-Toshkent-2012..